

Mission (im)possible: A call for action. Lessons learned from a pilot to share a complex, linked COVID-19 cohort dataset.

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Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic proved in a real-case scenario how rapid FAIR¹ sequence data sharing was used to inform public health response policies.² As a member of an international collaboration, the ReCoDID³ consortium was funded by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 programme, to develop a sustainable model for the storage, curation, and analyses of complex datasets collected from infectious disease related cohorts to facilitate and speed up outbreak research. Given the diversity of datasets and the complexity of sharing data from clinical research, a pilot study was developed within this project using COVID-19 data from Erasmus Medical Center (Erasmus MC) as a use-case (hereafter referred to as 'pilot'). The aim of the pilot was to test the potential for sharing linked laboratory data and clinical-epidemiological (CE) data in the evolving European infrastructure for open science as a proof of concept. In line with the rapidly evolving situation during the COVID-19 pandemic, we wanted to learn what it would take to release linked data from opportunistic studies, rather than pre-approved cohort data. The reason for this was that even pre-approved protocols fail to capture the potential breadth of information needed, and generated, during an emerging disease outbreak. For instance, even to date, the long-term consequences of COVID-19 in some patients are poorly understood, in part due to the lack of properly powered studies that include the in-depth measurements needed for pathogenesis research.

A second objective was to analyse the user needs, map the data types involved, define the possible barriers, and accelerate the technical developments of a connected dataset platform at EMBL-EBI, the intergovernmental European organisation specifically funded to facilitate sharing of (big) data in life sciences. Here, we describe experiences and lessons learned from this pilot, providing insights into the barriers and complexities of internationally sharing linked, complex cohort datasets for connected data analyses. We constructed an analytical timeline of events, describing key actions in the execution of the pilot, and a critical path, defining steps in the process of internationally sharing a linked cohort dataset.

This allowed us to determine where delays in the execution of the pilot occurred and to identify barriers that hindered the process. The pilot showed how building on existing infrastructure that had previously been developed within the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA⁴) at EMBL-EBI for pathogen genomics data sharing,^{5,6} allowed the rapid development of connected 'data hubs'. These data hubs were required to link human CE data under controlled access with open high dimensional laboratory data, for instance viral genomes, under FAIR principles. The datasets themselves and/or their connected data analysis were chosen as use-case and are not the focus of this manuscript.

Pilot set up

The following sections have references to the Timeline (Supplementary Material 1) in which the steps taken to set up and complete the pilot fall into the following categories: Data Identification and acquisition, Ethics & Legal requirements (data protection), Data Harmonisation, and Data storage & delivery.

The first step was to map the data landscape through meetings with basic researchers and clinical scientists that had generated COVID-19 data as part of pandemic related research,^{7,8,9} starting November 2020 (*Data Identification and acquisition*). Based on their input, a data map was drafted which illustrated how complex the seemingly 'simple' datasets (clinical, genomic, pathogen genomic and high-density laboratory) were, with different data sharing rules and governance for different parts of the datasets. The use of different identifiers and different platforms for data capture and storage became apparent during this task. In January 2021, a further meeting took place with the involved scientists to discuss existing datasets that could be linked in a pilot. A small cohort of SARS-CoV-2 positive patients (ICU and non-ICU) from the Erasmus MC was selected for whom several data types were partially available, including SARS-CoV-2 viral whole genomes, protein-microarray serological read-outs, T- and B-cell data as well as CE data.

Following this, the institute's legal and privacy offices were contacted in February 2021 to discuss the nature and aim of the COVID-19 pilot and the legal situation around sharing and linking CE data with high dimensional research data for the selected cohort, to be made available internationally through a platform to be established within the ReCoDID framework at the partner organisation EMBL-EBI (*Ethics & Legal requirements*). Further meetings took place with a team working on Erasmus MC's COVID-19 clinical database (established in June 2020 to include all hospitalised cases into an observational database) to discuss linking CE data with research datasets internally in compliance with the legal framework and how to request and gain access to the CE data for the specific individuals of the selected cohort. In total, 151 COVID-19 patients who had tested SARS-CoV-2 RT-PCR positive between May 2020 and May 2021 were selected for inclusion into this pilot, and a data access request for CE data was submitted to Erasmus MC's COVID-19 clinical database Management Team and approved in May 2021 (*Data Identification and acquisition*).

Linking of different data types

At the time of conducting this pilot, while submission of SARS-CoV-2 viral genomes to repositories such as EMBL-EBI's ENA⁴ (for raw sequences) and GISAID¹⁰ (for consensus sequences) was done routinely, other laboratory datasets (protein-microarrays, T- and B-cell data) were not shared. To link SARS-CoV-2

genomes to the other datasets, firstly, a check was done to verify whether viral genomes were available and had been submitted from the 151 individuals, or whether additional sequencing was needed. This exercise required iterative rounds of mapping four different identifiers to identify 63 individuals from whom 80 viral genomes had been submitted to EMBL-EBI's ENA. Since this pilot was conducted as a proof of concept, it was concluded that with the already sequenced viral genomes that link to this pilot no further sequencing was required. The internal datasets mapping exercise, which was completed in June 2021 (*Data Identification and acquisition*), further showed that serum antibody profiles generated using protein-microarrays were available for 40 patients, T-cell phenotype and reactivity data for 28 patients and clonal antibody cross-reactivity data using B-cell profiling for 17 patients out of 151 selected patients in the cohort. For seven patients out of 151 all data types were available.

Configuration of data infrastructure and Data delivery

In September 2021 (*Data storage & delivery*), meetings with representatives from various EMBL-EBI repositories (Figure 1) and Erasmus MC took place to identify suitable 'homes' for all other laboratory datasets (serum antibody profiles, T- and B-cell data). These meetings resulted in establishing a) whether and if so, where new pilot data types could be hosted and b) how the EMBL-EBI system could be leveraged to link all pilot datasets within the EMBL-EBI system, so that the datasets could be eventually also "presented" through a Cohort Browser,¹¹ which was being developed by the EMBL-EBI team. Although the EMBL-EBI repositories were not fully designed to host one of our data types (T-cell) it was possible to submit the outputs with some adjustments as a proof of concept. This leaves room for discussion between the respective researchers and the EMBL-EBI to allow for a more routine application.

Due to the extensive legal discussions around data sharing (*Table 1*), the implementation of the long-term model of the ReCoDID data workflow was brought to a standstill (*January 2021 start of legal discussions to Oct 2021 finalised ReCoDID Roadmap*). Therefore, after repositories that could host Erasmus MC's pilot datasets were determined, a slightly deviated data flow model for the pilot was agreed on (Figure 1). The deviation was solely focused on CE data and meant that instead of Heidelberg University Hospital (UKHD; tasked with harmonising CE data across cohorts) transferring harmonised CE data directly to the European Genome-Phenome Archive (EGA; EMBL-EBI), the harmonised CE data were transferred back from UKHD to Erasmus MC, and Erasmus MC carried out the CE data submission to EGA. The upload of the last Erasmus MC pilot datasets was completed on 28 November 2022 (*Data storage & delivery*). With the completion of linking all data types on participant level and presentation of all datasets through the Cohort Browser at EMBL-EBI,^{12,13} the pilot was considered as completed in December 2022.

Figure 1: Overview of Erasmus MC's pilot data flow, linkage and presentation for Erasmus MC's connected dataset pilot. Erasmus MC: mobilisation and consolidation of the datasets (*Data Identification and acquisition*) by the Erasmus MC team at the source within Erasmus MC, Participant-level and derived BioSample record registration, linking & submission of all data to repositories within the EMBL-EBI infrastructure including deposition of CE data under controlled access at EGA, setting up a DAC & DAA (*Data storage & delivery*); UKHD: harmonisation of the CE data & Data Dictionary at UKHD (*Data Harmonisation*); EMBL-EBI: provided the process for data linking on a participant level, including linking of the CE data to omics data types, using the hierarchical BioSamples database model & presentation of Erasmus MC's cohort study in the ReCoDID Cohort Browser (*Data storage & delivery*).

Barriers affecting the execution of the pilot

Several barriers significantly delayed the sharing of a linked dataset in this pilot, which are described in Table 1, as well as the main actor(s) influencing these barriers. As shown by the Timeline (Supplementary Material 1), the barriers associated with ethics and legal requirements, and with data identification and acquisition, caused the most evidential delays.

It is noteworthy that some of these barriers tended to reinforce each other, particularly due to shared underlying issues, such as the siloed nature of clinical and complex laboratory data collection and storage. At the start of the pilot, CE data was in different hospital systems, and not yet integrated into the (newly established) institute's database for COVID-19 patient related CE data. Furthermore, derived high dimensional laboratory data was stored in different systems, separate from patient- and diagnostic databases. This is a result of data being gathered by multiple different specialist teams, often for separately funded projects, as well as the lack of linked data infrastructures capturing both patient and

(raw) laboratory data, which is typical for hospital systems. Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic was characterised by a fragmented funding landscape. Many projects were funded, often focusing on a specific research question or field, thereby reinforcing the siloed nature of specialist teams' work. Also, for each of these projects, patient sample materials were needed (e.g. swabs, blood, serum). Consequently, high-dimensional lab data were generated for only a subset of patients, based on availability of sample material and requirements of the research topic (barrier “Insufficient interoperability of the data”).

Interestingly, the newly established institute’s database for COVID-19 CE data could in principle have worked as an enabler for data sharing. It was designed with the aim for CE data to be collected, stored and retrieved from one central database, and hence it could have addressed the issue of CE data being siloed in different existing hospital IT systems/ databases and improving the FAIR aspects of such data. Yet, a variety of implementation and operational issues, as described in Table 1, caused significant delays in CE data acquisition and sharing instead.

Table 1. The following crucial barriers significantly delayed the execution of the Erasmus MC pilot. In addition, the main actor(s) able to influence these barriers are identified, as well as the category of actions that each barrier is related to. The supervisory authorities (barrier “Adhering to GDPR, and difference in its interpretation”) refer to the independent public authority/ies in each Member State responsible for monitoring the application of the GDPR.

Barrier description	Actors	Category of actions
Adhering to GDPR, and differences in its interpretation. The data workflow gave rise to legal issues in the context of the GDPR, with regards to GDPR roles (e.g., controller vs processor), potential liabilities, different interpretations of Article 49 (Derogations for specific situations), also in regard to the transfer of data to international organisations (here: EMBL-EBI), resulted in long-lasting legal discussions to define the process of data flow within ReCoDID.	EU and national governments; supervisory authorities	Ethics & legal requirements
Insufficient FAIRification and sharing of initial data, due to a lack of mandatory FAIRification and sharing rules, insufficient time and resources to do so - especially during the pandemic, when time and resources were scarce and often differently prioritised - and competing priorities (FAIRification and data sharing is not main priority).	Academic hospitals/ institutes; Researchers; EU and national funding agencies	Data identification & acquisition; Data storage & delivery
Insufficient interoperability of the data. Establishing linkages between CE data and corresponding high-dimensional lab data was challenging, and the availability of overlapping data types was limited. Various identifiers were used for CE data and derived high dimensional laboratory data, and metadata was not fully harmonised, making it difficult to establish linkages. Furthermore, as high dimensional data types were generated in separately funded projects, a limited amount of overlap in high-dimensional data types existed for the patients.	Academic hospitals/ institutes; Researchers; EU and national funding agencies	Data identification & acquisition
Issues contributing to difficulty in CE data acquisition. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Competing priorities: There was a plethora of clinical studies by specialists from a broad range of disciplines that had to be entered into the institute’s COVID-19 CE database. Consequently, there were difficulties in getting approval for prioritisation for this project of data entry into the institute’s COVID-19 CE database and data access. Furthermore, over time there was a 	Academic hospitals/ institutes	Data identification & acquisition

<p>reduced interest with decreasing burden of COVID in completing the data entry of CE data.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time consuming and resource intensive handling and storage of CE data: CE data was stored at different specialised hospital health record systems, that allowed only partial automation of data entry into the institute’s COVID-19 CE database, and records needed to be administered individually. Hence, this was a time consuming and resource intensive process, during a time when clinical services were overburdened with COVID-19 cases and resulted in a backlog of CE data that needed to be entered into the institute’s COVID-19 CE database. • Discontinued institutional funding and support for its CE database for COVID-19 data: After one year, the institute’s COVID-19 CE database was discontinued and subsequently placed under different management. This also meant that additional requirements, e.g. related to data protection and ethics, had to be met before CE data could be accessed and shared. 		
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Enablers contributing to the execution of the pilot

In Table 2, the factors that contributed to or facilitated the sharing of a linked dataset in this pilot are described, as well as the main actor(s) to influence these enablers, and showed the willingness of the involved teams to overcome the barriers in the sharing of a complex, linked dataset.

Beyond the below mentioned enabler “building forward on existing collaborations”, a noteworthy effort was made by participants in this pilot, especially the clinical and laboratory researchers who were not directly involved in the ReCoDID project, which contributed to data access, data conversion according to FAIR principles, and data sharing. However, despite these efforts, delays in data acquisition and data storage and their delivery existed, due to insufficient priority (see barrier “Insufficient FAIRification and sharing of initial data”), resulting in delayed submission of data as shown in the timeline (Supplementary Material 1).

Table 2. Enablers that facilitated the execution of the ReCoDID Erasmus MC pilot. In addition, the main actor(s) able to influence these enablers are identified, as well as the category of actions that each enabler is related to.

Enablers	Actors	Category of actions
<p>Active support from legal advisors/GDPR specialists. Navigating the complexity of regulations governing data sharing, such as the GDPR, and to apply these accordingly, requires expert legal knowledge. The active support from legal/GDPR specialists was therefore pivotal in defining the process of data flow within ReCoDID.</p>	Academic hospitals/ institutes	Ethics & legal requirements
<p>Building forward on existing infrastructure for sharing (biomedical) data, allowed the rapid development of the connected data hubs to include controlled access sensitive data for/in this pilot.</p>	Researchers; EU	Data storage & delivery
<p>Building forward on existing collaborations, as developed in ReCoDID and COMPARE,^{5,14} facilitated the steps in the pilot and helped to further build trust necessary for data sharing between participants. The collaboration between the data provider/controller (Erasmus MC) and the respective EMBL-EBI repositories, as well as between the EMBL-EBI repositories, was needed in this pilot to drive</p>	Researchers; EU	All

further developments and to extend the existing infrastructures to host and present connected datasets.		
Dedicated data scientist championing the pilot. Acquiring data from different sources/systems and collected by various specialist teams, linking such data, and ensuring the (legal) requirements are fulfilled before sharing such data, is cumbersome and time-consuming. A dedicated data scientist, supported by the constant encouragement and advocacy of the principal investigator for data sharing amongst researchers, ensured the pilot kept moving ahead.	Academic hospitals/ institutes	Mainly data identification & acquisition

Critical path for sharing a complex, linked dataset

The critical path analysis (Figure 2) defined the steps in the process of sharing a complex, linked cohort dataset based on our pilot experiences, and were classified into the four categories of actions: data identification and acquisition (4 steps), ethics and legal requirements (7 steps), external data harmonisation (1 step), and data storage and delivery (5 steps). As depicted in Figure 2, most of the steps in this process could be worked on concurrently, depending on the availability of resources (e.g., time of legal staff; availability of appropriate, standardised legal templates). As CE data harmonisation was performed at another participating institute, this is indicated as a separate step, for which also steps in the category ethics and legal requirements had to be completed first. Interestingly, before data could be submitted and shared through the appropriate infrastructure, pathogen genetic sequence data (GSD) required a minimum number of steps (1 step), followed by other laboratory data (6 steps), whereas CE data required at least 10 steps. This also corresponds to the time for completion of all steps for each of the data types, with the least amount of time for pathogen GSD data (Supplementary Material 1). However, it should be noted that if pathogen GSD is not routinely submitted and shared (in near real-time), i.e. no institutional submission route has been established, it would follow the path of other lab data except for the two legal steps regarding informed consent.

Figure 2. Critical path for sharing a complex, linked dataset. Two rounded boxes mark the start and endpoint; the diamond box represents a decision before steps in the process can be taken. Steps were classified into the four categories of actions: data identification and acquisition (4 steps, shown in text boxes with blue margins), ethics and legal requirements (7 steps, shown in red), external data harmonisation (1 step, shown in purple), and data storage and delivery (5 steps, shown in green). Dashed green boxes represent steps that were needed for this first pilot to build the system (built by EMBL-EBI). However, for any future data sharing using this system, these steps would not need to be taken again.

Mission (im)possible: a call for action

As demonstrated in this pilot, sharing a linked cohort dataset using a centralised approach can succeed, but several crucial barriers exist that cause long delays. Although these barriers have been extensively described previously,^{15,16,17} they persist today, as currently the burden to overcome or circumvent such barriers is placed on the individual researchers, projects, or institutes. However, the root causes to these barriers are systemic in nature such as the increasing complexity in and accumulation of national and regional regulations, the insufficient incorporation of the international data sharing process in data protection laws, as well as the lack of incentives for FAIR and open data sharing in the academic reward and recognition system. To alleviate these barriers, stakeholders at institutional, national and international/EU level (e.g. governments, healthcare, research, journals, funders, legal) need to work jointly towards building a model that not only supports but enforces data exchange by simplifying steps

in the process of data sharing, taking privacy and legal aspects into account and to reward researchers in new ways.¹⁸ Below we describe some immediate actions to achieve this based on our pilot experiences.

At EU/International level

Support with privacy questions and GDPR: Currently, sharing CE data in compliance with GDPR, or finding solutions to work around GDPR barriers, is placed at the burden of institutes and researchers. We recommend creating a roadmap amongst EU countries for how to deal with common issues, to avoid (recurrent) lengthy legal discussions. Harmonisation of regional and national implementation of GDPR, and alleviation of the disproportionate burden in legal compliance activities for data sharing with international organisations, needs to be achieved. This was recently also concluded by Science Europe in their feedback on the implementation of the GDPR.¹⁹ Finally, additional support should be provided by the EU to funded projects that want to link and share CE or otherwise sensitive data internationally and for which the GDPR is likely creating a barrier to do so, for example, by providing legal guidance or a top up for projects to hire legal experts.

Build and maintain FAIR data sharing during ‘peacetime’: Provision of specified support for funded projects to FAIRify and share data could enhance data sharing. Mandatory FAIRification of data in funded projects with funding for personnel to build and maintain FAIR data collections and FAIR sharing is often missing and would be required as a step towards data sharing. Current procedures require applicants to only describe in a Data Management Plan (DMP) how data sharing will be done, but there is neither an obligation to do so, nor monitoring of and consequences for non-compliance exist. At the same time, more data repositories submitting to evaluation-based initiatives and accreditation processes (such as the TRUST,²⁰ ELIXIR Core Data Resources,²¹ and Global Core Biodata Resources,²² could help with a cultural change towards more FAIR data sharing. Furthermore, FAIRification and sharing of data (e.g. via existing repositories) should become standard practice during the education of bachelor, master, and PhD students.

Decrease fragmented funding landscape: Consideration for funding more interdisciplinary projects is important to study and answer combined research questions. However, the current funding landscape is often fragmented, and narrow topic focused, making combined data sharing more difficult. When providing funding for monodisciplinary/specialised projects, it should be at least ensured to make FAIRification and sharing of datasets mandatory. Furthermore, continued funding support for existing data infrastructures is key to sustaining the efforts of data FAIRification and sharing, both nationally and internationally.

Willingness and commitment building: We call for establishment of a common policy about data sharing allowing culture change at the EU/international level and for provision of resources to do so. One way of supporting culture change can be achieved by reflecting how researchers are recognised/rewarded/assessed beyond publishing results in a journal. This could be elevated by changing publication policies (working with journals and funders) to truly attribute data sharing and data exchange. A culture change could also be helped with firm policies to put good practices in place, such as acknowledging data providers when re-using datasets from other groups, and/or the use of citable data

Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) pointing to their data (e.g. as used for one of the datasets used in this pilot).²³

At Institutional and national level

Standardisation and interoperability: Institutes need to prioritise standardisation or reconciliation of existing databases and systems to tackle data siloes. Currently, a lack of interoperability between hospital and research data systems is common. Furthermore, 'in-house' hospital formats are being used for data collection. Where possible, harmonisation of laboratory protocols allowing for more standardised data output formats could increase interoperability. During the COVID-19 pandemic, clinical researchers' lack of time, and in the absence of specialised staff, such as data stewards, harmonisation of CE data according to international standards (WHO - ISARIC format)²⁴ was delayed or not completed. Overarching infrastructures at Medical Centres/University Hospitals that would allow and enhance standardisation, harmonisation, and linking of different data types locally and nationally could also increase interoperability at EU/international level.²⁵

Willingness and commitment building: At the institute level, common policy about data sharing should also be established, and resources provided to do so, allowing for a culture change to happen. The decision to share data, time and resources that need to be spent on going through all steps, are currently with (clinical) researchers, leading to different sharing norms and cultures, often considered as 'ownership' and/or a 'burden' rather than a common good. This should be supported by an EU wide policy (see above). Finally, institutes should establish clear institutional guidelines on data systems, access protocols, legal/ethics protocols, invest in GDPR legal experts, designated people/offices to work with, and a catalogue of data resources adhering to appropriate standards of service.

Conclusions

Without action, barriers for data sharing will persist, especially for sharing CE data. Instead, decentralised or federated approaches are now often preferred, as these are circumventing barriers,^{26,27,28} and are less resource- and time intensive for (clinical) researchers and institutes. Benefits and consequences of existing data sharing models are known (Table 3). Federated networks, where decentralised but interconnected nodes allow data to be queried or analysed by other nodes in the network without the data leaving its location, have been proposed as a solution and are being worked on to address the siloing of health data and current barriers to data sharing.²⁹ However, common obstacles to broader uptake of federated networks include the absence of data standards or limited adherence to existing standards, the complexity of designing, implementing and deploying federated solutions that preserve privacy.³⁰ The challenges are reported to arise even between partners with shared ambitions, and must be addressed before federated networks can be implemented more widely, especially across national borders.²⁹ Therefore, it is difficult to predict when federated networks can be more widely used. The utility of federated analysis may one day be sufficient to outweigh the additional delays associated with moving some data across borders, but the question remains if full federation will ever be possible. In Europe, a more federated approach may be taken with the European Commission's adoption of a proposal for legislation establishing the European Health Data Space (EHDS), in which re-use or

secondary use of health data will be subject to authorisation by national health data access bodies.³¹ Some countries have already established a health data access body, including Finland, France, Denmark, and Norway, granting access to health data based upon a permit, with national legislation stipulating which data can be processed in which way and under which conditions. While costs incurred by data controllers for the extraction and delivery of data is included in the permit price, thereby limiting financial burden for institutes to share their data, pricing of permits to access and re-use health data may introduce new paywalls and thus lead to inequality, especially for researchers in low- and middle-income countries as the pricing of data permits for applicants outside the EU is much higher.³² In addition, significant delays have been reported for data permit approval to access health data.³³

However, the first and uppermost question needs to be answered at institutional and national level: Do people want to share data and what are they prepared to invest in terms of a collaborative effort to do so, if there was funding, GDPR and other support, for data sharing to move away from a felt 'burden' to being a seen 'benefit'. Several studies suggest that efforts at promoting data sharing and reuse should be aimed at solving not only technological problems, but also addressing researchers' and other stakeholders' concerns about sharing 'their' data.^{15,34,35}

Table 3. Main benefits and consequences of existing data sharing models.

Data Sharing Models	
Centralised	Decentralised/federated
<p>Benefits: hosting and curation of large datasets necessary for improved prediction and preparedness on global, EU and national level; Standardised data input and output leading to interoperability, easing re-analysis by others.</p> <p>Consequence: actions need to be taken to improve the process of such sharing (see our recommendations).</p>	<p>Benefits: circumventing barriers, less resource and time intensive for (clinical) researchers and institutes; do not have to move data;</p> <p>Consequence: no sharing or limited sharing and linking of datasets, likely result in increased fragmentation, difficulty to apply federated data analyses across a wide range of data formats and sources, predictions and preparedness more at local/regional level, some approaches likely increase inequality.</p>

The field of genomics has often led the way in (medical) biology data sharing,³⁶ due to investments to build international databases for genomic data, and long-standing policies for sequence data sharing.^{37,38} Furthermore, except for human genomics, privacy and data protection concerns have been (partly) overcome due to the development of common principles including benefit sharing, when it comes to sharing GSD, including pathogen genomes.^{39,40} During the COVID-19 pandemic, in countries where previous investments had been made in sequencing infrastructure, and where trained staff for sequence interpretation and software developing capacities were available (investments in peacetime made), it was shown that near real-time sharing of viral genomic data is possible. However, ongoing discussions to include digital sequence information, including viral genomic data,⁴¹ under the Nagoya protocol,⁴² or the WHO CA+,⁴³ could potentially result in new barriers, as in the critical path of GSD steps to complete legal procedures before sharing data would be added. Implementing this change may considerably delay the prompt sharing and access to GSD, which has proven crucial in early detection, diagnostics, and

identifying variants during the COVID-19 pandemic,² while its impact on improving access and benefit sharing mechanisms remains uncertain.⁴⁴ Consequently, there is not only a need to streamline the timeliness of steps for sharing CE and other data, but also ensuring no additional barriers are created in the process of sharing a linked cohort dataset.

The multidisciplinary nature of infectious disease research and collaborations reflects the complexity of research and public health questions which need to be understood and answered around (re-) emerging diseases, whether they arise by an adaptation strategy as part of the pathogen's evolution, or caused by human factors or behavior, global connectivity and changes in ecology and climate. While certain answers can be found in isolation within a specific area of research and small numbers of patients, larger complex questions require a joint outlook and a combination of data sources to be examined together.⁴⁵

Here we have shown the complexities in sharing a small but complex, linked dataset from opportunistic COVID-19 clinical and laboratory research studies as done in (academic) hospital settings. Combining results from multidisciplinary research for overarching analysis requires systems that work towards structured and harmonised data production in the first place, and data linkage and sharing as a next step. In addition to the need for suitable and easy-to-use platforms for data linkage and sharing, several other factors identified here such as regulatory, ethics, motivational and operational challenges, often lead to hesitancy in data sharing, whereas at the times of emergency everything needs to happen in a timely manner. We also provided actionable elements to shorten the timeline to go through this process. Actions that are taken now to improve data sharing for outbreak preparedness and response will improve our ability to detect and respond to emerging threats in the future. A 100-days mission approach has been adopted for identifying barriers to product discovery and streamlining timelines for rapid initial authorisation and manufacturing at scale of pandemic products.⁴⁶ We call upon governments, funders, global and regional organisations, scientists, journals and industries to take a similar approach to tackle known barriers hampering (cohort) data sharing for infectious disease preparedness and response.

Authors' contributions

Although the datasets themselves and/or their connected data analysis are not the focus of this manuscript, the pilot study, to share a complex linked COVID-19 cohort dataset, would not have been possible without the respective data providers. Data providers were BOM, RdV, GvN, RS, JvB and EvG. FT carried out clinical-epidemiological data harmonisation. Funding acquisition was done by TJ, MK, MvR, GC. CA and GR carried out the project administration (management and coordination responsibility for the pilot planning and execution at Erasmus MC and EMBL-EBI respectively). The project was conceptualised and the manuscript conceived by MvR, CA, MK. Writing-original draft was carried out by CA, MvR, and, Writing-review & editing by all authors. Figures were designed by MvR, GR. Visualisation (preparation, creation and presentation of work at consortium meetings) was done by CA and MvR. CA and MvR contributed equally to this work.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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References

1. Wilkinson M., Dumontier M., Aalbersberg I., *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* **3**, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
2. Oude Munnink B.B., Nieuwenhuijse D.F., Stein M., *et al.* Rapid SARS-CoV-2 whole-genome sequencing and analysis for informed public health decision-making in the Netherlands. *Nat Med* **26**, 1405–1410 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-020-0997-y>
3. ReCoDID, Reconciliation of Cohort Data in Infectious Diseases. <https://recodid.eu/>. Accessed 20 December 2023.
4. European Nucleotide Archive (ENA). <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>. Accessed 16 January 2024.
5. Clara Amid, Nima Pakseresht, Nicole Silvester, *et al.* The COMPARE Data Hubs, *Database*, Volume 2019, 2019, baz136, <https://doi.org/10.1093/database/baz136>
6. Nadim Rahman, Colman O’Cathail, Ahmad Zyoud, *et al.* Mobilisation and analyses of publicly available SARS-CoV-2 data for pandemic responses. *Microbial Genomics* (in press). bioRxiv 2023.04.19.537514; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.04.19.537514>
7. Aguilar-Bretones M, Westerhuis BM, Raadsen MP, *et al.* Seasonal coronavirus-specific B cells with limited SARS-CoV-2 cross-reactivity dominate the IgG response in severe COVID-19. *J Clin Invest.* 2021;**131**(21):e150613. <https://doi.org/10.1172/JCI150613>.
8. Lu L, Sikkema RS, Velkers FC, Nieuwenhuijse DF, *et al.* Adaptation, spread and transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in farmed minks and associated humans in the Netherlands. *Nat Commun.* 2021 Nov 23;**12**(1):6802. doi: 10.1038/s41467-021-27096-9. PMID: 34815406; PMCID: PMC8611045.
9. Haagmans BL, Koopmans MPG. Spreading of SARS-CoV-2 from hamsters to humans. *The Lancet Comment* **399**, 10329, 1027-1028, March 12, 2022
10. GISAID. <https://gisaid.org>. Accessed 16 January 2024.
11. Cohort Browser. Infectious disease cohort studies shared at EMBL-EBI. <https://www.pathogensportal.org/cohorts?query=BSC0000010> Accessed 20 December 2023.
12. Stroe O. First linked dataset on Pathogens Portal. EMBL-EBI News. Published online 20 December 2022. Accessed 10 December 2023.

13. BioSamples. EMBL-EBI. Search results for ReCoDID COVID-19 pilot study. Accessed 20 December 2023. <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biosamples/samples?text=ReCoDID%20COVID-19%20pilot%20study>
14. COMPARE. Collaborative management platform for detection and analyses for (re-)emerging and foodborne outbreaks in Europe. <https://www.compare-europe.eu/> Accessed 17 January 2024.
15. Ribeiro CdS, van Roode MY, Haringhuizen GB, Koopmans MPG, Claassen E, van de Burgwal LHM. How ownership rights over microorganisms affect infectious disease control and innovation: A root-cause analysis of barriers to data sharing as experienced by key stakeholders. *PLoS One* 2018; **13**(5).
16. Bernier A., Molnár-Gábor F., Knoppers B.M. *et al.* Reconciling the biomedical data commons and the GDPR: three lessons from the EUCAN ELSI collaboratory. *Eur J Hum Genet* (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41431-023-01403-y>
17. Vlahou A, Hallinan D, Apweiler R, *et al.* Data sharing under the General Data Protection Regulation: Time to harmonize law and research ethics? *Hypertension* **77**, 4, p1029-35.
18. European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Maxwell, L., *Maximising investments in health research – FAIR data for a coordinated COVID-19 response – Workshop report*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/726950>
19. Science Europe. Science Europe Feedback on the Implementation of the GDPR. Brussels, 8 February 2024, Available via https://scienceeurope.org/media/5blavcwx/se_response_ec_consultation_gdpr_implementation_final.pdf Accessed 16 February 2024.
20. Lin D., Crabtree J., Dillo I. *et al.* The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Sci Data* **7**, 144 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>
21. ELIXIR Core Data Resources. <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/core-data-resources/> Accessed 12 February 2024.
22. Global Core Biodata Resources. <https://globalbiodata.org/what-we-do/global-core-biodata-resources/> Accessed 12 February 2024.
23. Oude Munnink B., Nieuwenhuijse D., Sikkema R., Koopmans M.P.G., *et al.* On behalf of the Dutch national COVID-19 response team (2021). SARS-CoV-2 whole-genome sequencing for informed public health decision making and outbreak tracking and tracing in the Netherlands. *BioStudies*, S-BSST662. <https://doi.org/10.6019/S-BSST662>
24. ISARIC. International Severe Acute Respiratory and Emerging Infection Consortium. <https://isaric.org/research-2/covid-19-clinical-research-resources/covid-19-crf/> Accessed 9 January 2024.
25. Rinaldi E., Stellmach C., Rajkumar N.M.R. *et al.* Harmonization and standardization of data for a pan-European cohort on SARS- CoV-2 pandemic. *npj Digit. Med.* **5**, 75 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41746-022-00620-x>
26. Marcon Y, Bishop T, Avraam D, *et al.* Orchestrating privacy-protected big data analyses of data from different resources with R and DataSHIELD. *PLoS Comput Biol* **17**(3):e1008880
27. Peñalvo JL, Mertens E, Ademović E, *et al.* Unravelling data for rapid evidence-based response to COVID-19: a summary of the unCoVer protocol. *BMJ Open* 2021;11:e055630. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2021-055630
28. Tacconelli E, Gorska A, Carrara E, Davis RJ, Bonten M, Friedrich AW, Glasner C, Goossens H, Hasenauer J, Abad JMH, Peñalvo JL, Sanchez-Niubo A, Sialm A, Scipione G, Soriano G, Yazdanpanah Y, Vorstenbosch E, Jaenisch T. Challenges of data sharing in European Covid-19 projects: A learning opportunity for advancing pandemic preparedness and response. *Lancet Reg Health Eur.* 2022

Oct;21:100467. doi: 10.1016/j.lanepe.2022.100467. Epub 2022 Aug 4. PMID: 35942201; PMCID: PMC9351292.

29. Hallock H, Marshall SE, 't Hoen PAC, Nygård JF, Hoorne B, Fox C and Alagaratnam S (2021) Federated Networks for Distributed Analysis of Health Data. *Front. Public Health* 9:712569. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2021.712569

30. James Casaletto, Alexander Bernier, Robyn McDougall, Melissa S. Cline. Federated Analysis for Privacy-Preserving Data Sharing: A Technical and Legal Primer. *Annual Review of Genomics and Human Genetics* 2023 24:1, 347-368

31. European Parliamentary Research Service (EPRS). European Health Data Space. At a Glance, December 2023.

[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/ATAG/2023/754642/EPRS_ATA\(2023\)754642_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/ATAG/2023/754642/EPRS_ATA(2023)754642_EN.pdf)

Accessed 9 January 2024

32. FINDATA. Social and Health Data Permit Authority. Pricing. <https://findata.fi/en/pricing/> Accessed 9 January 2024.

33. Lähteenmäki J, Vuorinen A-L, Pajula J, et al. Integrating data from multiple Finnish biobanks and national health-care registers for retrospective studies: Practical experiences. *Scandinavian Journal of Public Health*. 2022;50(4):482-489. doi:10.1177/14034948211004421

34. Federer LM, Lu YL, Joubert DJ, Welsh J, Brandys B. Biomedical Data Sharing and Reuse: Attitudes and Practices of Clinical and Scientific Research Staff. *PLoS One*. 2015 Jun 24;10(6):e0129506. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0129506. PMID: 26107811; PMCID: PMC4481309.

35. van Roode M.Y., dos S. Ribeiro C., Farag E. *et al.* Six dilemmas for stakeholders inherently affecting data sharing during a zoonotic (re-)emerging infectious disease outbreak response. *BMC Infect Dis* 24, 185 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12879-024-09054-0>

36. Nanda S., Kowalczyk M.K. Unpublished genomic data—how to share? *BMC Genomics* 15, 5 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2164-15-5>

37. Marshall E. Bermuda rules: community spirit, with teeth. *Science*. 2001, 291 (5507): 1192-10.1126/science.291.5507.1192.

38. World Health Organization (WHO). Policy statement on data sharing by the World Health Organization in the context of public health emergencies. 13 April 2016. [Microsoft Word - SPG data sharing 13apr16 \(final\) \(2\).docx \(who.int\)](#) Accessed 21 December 2023.

39. Sixty-fourth World Health Assembly. Pandemic influenza preparedness: sharing of influenza viruses and access to vaccines and other benefits. Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization; WHA64.5. https://apps.who.int/gb/ebwha/pdf_files/WHA64-REC1/A64_REC1-en.pdf Accessed 16 January 2024.

40. Fidler DP, Gostin LO. The WHO Pandemic Influenza Preparedness Framework: A Milestone in Global Governance for Health. *JAMA*. 2011;306(2):200–201. doi:10.1001/jama.2011.960

41. Scholz A.H., Freitag J., Lyal C.H.C. *et al.* Multilateral benefit-sharing from digital sequence information will support both science and biodiversity conservation. *Nat Commun* 13, 1086 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-28594-0>

42. Convention on Biological Diversity (United Nations). Nagoya protocol on access to genetic resources and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from their utilization to the convention on biological diversity. <https://www.cbd.int/abs/doc/protocol/nagoya-protocol-en.pdf> Accessed 22 December 2023.

43. World Health Organization (WHO). Bureau's text of the WHO convention, agreement, or other international instrument on pandemic prevention, preparedness and response (WHO CA+) for the

consideration of the Intergovernmental Negotiating Body at its fifth meeting. 2 June 2023.

https://apps.who.int/gb/inb/pdf_files/inb5/A_INB5_6-en.pdf Accessed 12 December 2023.

44. DSI Scientific Network. Using digital sequence information (DSI) to design an mRNA vaccine: COVID-19 case study.

<https://www.dsiscientificnetwork.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/DSI-covid-vaccines-factsheet.pdf>

Accessed 11 December 2023.

45. Eckhardt M., Hultquist J.F., Kaake R.M. *et al.* A systems approach to infectious disease. *Nat Rev Genet* **21**, 339–354 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41576-020-0212-5>

46. 100 Days mission to respond to future pandemic threats. A report to the G7 by the International Pandemic Preparedness Secretariat. [100-Days-Mission-2nd-Implementation-Report-1.pdf](#)

<https://d7npznmd5zvwd.cloudfront.net>) Accessed 21 December 2023.

Supplementary Material

Timeline

First part of the analytical timeline is marked by continuous talks with Erasmus MC lab and clinical researchers, legal offices, the institutional clinical database team, and EBI:

The timeline is depicted at the bottom, with actions chronologically positioned and clustered according to the type of actions they related to. Actions related to the identification and acquisition of the data are depicted within blue boxes; actions related to ethics and legal requirements regarding data protection and privacy in red, with additional actions related to ethics and legal requirements performed at Erasmus MC due to GDPR delays (deviated pilot model) in yellow, while actions related to the data storage and delivery through a centralised approach are depicted in green boxes. Dashed boxes represent actions that were not specifically executed in the context of this pilot but had an influence on the timeliness of (other) actions in the pilot. DAC: data access committee; DAA: data access agreement; DPA: data processing agreement; DPIA: data protection impact assessment.

Second part of the analytical timeline is marked by actions to adhere to legal requirements in collaboration with legal offices, data harmonisation of CE data in collaboration with UKHD, and finally data submission to in collaboration with the researchers and EBI:

The timeline is depicted at the bottom, with actions chronologically positioned and clustered according to the type of actions they related to. Actions related to the identification and acquisition of the data are depicted within blue boxes; actions related to ethics and legal requirements regarding data protection and privacy in red, with additional actions related to ethics and legal requirements performed at Erasmus MC due to GDPR delays (deviated pilot model) in yellow; actions related to (external) data harmonisation in purple boxes, while actions related to the data storage and delivery through a centralised approach are depicted in green boxes. Dashed boxes represent actions that were not specifically executed in the context of this pilot, yet had an influence on the timeliness of (other) actions in the pilot. DAC: data access committee; DAA: data access agreement; DPA: data processing agreement; DPIA: data protection impact assessment.